

PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN RAPID ACQUISITION OF ENGLISH

Davronova Fotima Pirnazarovna

Samarkand state university veterinary medicine of livestock and biotechnologies

ANNOTATION

The article highlights the effective results of focusing on educational activities in the form of computer games and Web quests in the rapid teaching of English to students in the context of digital technologies, based on examples. This is explained on the basis of examples of how it can be done by using methods that create multiple learning opportunities. A new subject in English is discussed as effective when conducted with the active participation of all students based on Web quests, computer games, and cloud technologies.

Key words: digital technology, cloud technology, web-quest, acquisition, educational program, communication.

The use of the following information and communication technologies in teaching English serves to improve the quality of education, to develop students' creativity, and to learn the English language perfectly: programmed education, interactive dialogue, computer visualization of educational information, computer modeling, and the use of educational programs. One of the technologies used in higher education institutions and ready to give effective results is Microsoft Cloud cloud technologies.

In teaching English to students, cloud technology has a great effect on their knowledge acquisition, because information complex technologies are more convenient than conventional technologies. Based on the available literature, researched scientific and internet sources, we present the following description of the concept of "cloud technology":

Cloud technology is a type of digital technology that serves to gather, sort, collect and interpret information that can be stored on cloud platforms within the scope of options:

- Types of cloud technologies
- Virtual office;
- Virtual call center;
- Hosting for corporate mail and internet;
- Cloud Application Rental and more

Cloud computing is a technology that delivers digital data to Internet users, in our case, students of a higher education institution, in the form of an online service. When using cloud technologies in English classes, the computer programs used by the student can display the work results in the local web browser window. All the applications necessary for work can be on a remote Internet server and temporarily stored in the cache of the student's laptop, set-top box, phone (organizing the database). In this case, the user of the Internet service has his own database, does not care about the infrastructure of the infrastructure that stores the information, and may not worry about the operating system and software.

The word "cloud" means "symbol", "excerpt" and refers to a complex infrastructure with a technical structure.

In cloud technologies, the order of work in files is important because of its convenience. First of all, the availability of the software, or the presence of a flash card, the size of the data on the hard disk of the computer, whether the programs have a license or not, the possibility of transmitting information to several people in one second, etc., indicate its convenience. In order to use cloud technology in English classes, it can be used to "conduct negotiations", "make customers interested in buying products", "tell works of art" by "engaging" students in the fields of business, sports, art through the Internet. For example, getting a discount can be organized as a quest, and sales as a game.

Digital technologies can also be effectively used in the teaching of educational courses related to pedagogic subjects. For example, managing students' imagined "employees", building relationships in the team, improving work efficiency - all this will be more effective if it is conducted on the basis of Web quests. Web-quest is one of the newest means of using information and communication technologies to conduct training or participate in activities outside the classroom, and it is mainly intended for students involved in the educational process.

Educational quest is considered as a pedagogical technology, which is implemented with the help of information and communication.

It is known that the Web-quest, which is used as a didactic game, can be formed on the basis of Cloud technologies and becomes one of the methods of increasing the motivation of students. Recruiting new professionals can also be done as a game. For example, a "newbie" goes through various quest levels, gets to know the company, answers interviews in English, solves tests. And if it reaches the highest level, then the chances of winning are high.

Cloud technologies can be further used to keep customers on site longer. For example, the following text could be used in a Web-quest with students on the topic "Essay on Sports":

Steps used in the quest process:

Essay on Sports

Hello, folks! Have you ever heard of this well-known saying: "A sound mind in a sound body"? I think the answer in most cases is "yes". So, we're discussing the importance of sports today.

Not so long ago sports was really important part of our day to day life. But with the rising popularity of television, the Internet and video games, sports and exercises are not so important anymore. There is a reason why we should do sports on daily basis. Going in for sports means to be energetic and healthy. While people who are not keen on it are often seen struggling with illnesses in their adulthood, such as diabetes, obesity etc; Moreover, it helps us not only to improve our body but our mind as well.

People who are good at sports also show a lifestyle of excellent quality. They are more active, can make better decisions and find the way out of stressful situations. Not encouraging children to take part in sports activities can make them lazy and peevish as they turn into grown-ups. Also, people who participate in sports competitions are more successful. It is a well-known fact that a man involved in sports activity from the very young age develops a very strong personality. He cultivates what is called the leadership.

For children who want to do sports besides physical training lessons, special facilities are created. In our city, there is a great amount of gyms for fitness, swimming pools, stadiums. Don't forget about an Ice Palace, where you can enjoy playing hockey and ice-skating. Everyone has an opportunity to do sports if they want to.

And as for me, I can't live without sports. In summer me and my friend go jogging every morning, and when I have free time I attend the gym and swimming pool. And one more important thing according to the Olympics motto, "It's not the winning, but the participation."

Never forget that sports is an essential part of our life.

Excitement in the quest, the activity of the participants of the quest will increase. This is what is needed to make the participants of the training a "living" community.

Prize-proponents of Quest believe that the reward principle is the best tool for new technologies. This process increases the activity of the participants, but it is very important that the prize is interesting for the player. The quest helps to solve the issue of motivation in a new, non-standard way.

Motivation-this is considered the foundation on which any quest is based on the principle, and since the participants of the study need to interact with each other, they use the simplest options for motivation-encouragement, status, etc. If the

communication takes place in an external environment, for example with customers, the motivation can be service, convenience, free product.

Increase reputation-every student wants to be recognized in the community as a person of his own worth. Quest proposes to do this through the principle of status. Surprisingly, even a prize cannot motivate students to continue their studies with the same enthusiasm as receiving the gratitude of the team and teachers. Today, the most popular for language learning: Arena, AnyLogic, SIMSCRIPT, SLAM, SIMAN, AweSim, GPSS can be used. World-leading corporations such as Microsoft, Nike, American Express, and Samsung are paying attention to the use of digital technologies in the educational process. The methodology for using new technologies in language learning is defined within the chosen object.

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